

Digital transformations in healthcare: Improving the pace of change by demo videos

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ABSTRACT

During the COVID-19 pandemic, organizations were forced to digitally transform their business in a timely manner. Especially the healthcare sector has faced unexpected needs for rapid digitization and acceptance of technological innovations. Previous research does not identify if training, in particular with the use of demo videos, impacts the pace of digital transformation within hospitals. Based on this, the following research question is formulated: “*What is the influence of demo videos as a training method on the pace of digital transformation in the healthcare sector?*”. Literature research and interviews with experts who have experience in digital transformation in healthcare were used to collect data. The results showed that demo videos can improve the pace of change by improving user acceptance, which is improved by the flexibility of demo video training and the creation of engagement of people. This research contributes to the quality of healthcare by creating more flexible and (modern-)digital hospitals. Future research can statistically prove the recommendations by conducting an experiment.

Keywords - Digital transformation, Healthcare, Pace of change, Training method, Demo videos

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformations influence all organizations. A digital transformation can be defined as the process of digitization (the process of transforming physical format to a digital version) and the adoption of new technologies (Fernandez-Vidal et al., 2022). Digitization has various goals. Researchers refer to digital transformation as when technologies are used to modify existing business models, optimize business processes, or support organizational transformations. External environmental factors can cause the need of (rapid) digitization as was shown by the COVID-19 pandemic. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, organizations had to digitize quickly to continue providing their services.

Especially the healthcare sector has faced unexpected needs for rapid digitization and adjustment to technological innovations. Where stakeholders such as policymakers, hospitals, and healthcare professionals were previously reluctant to digitize processes, it offered great opportunities during the pandemic. This made people adopt technological innovations faster (Bhambere et. al., 2021). Literature has noted the use and impact of healthcare specific digital transformations, such as health cloud, mobile health, clinical decision support systems, and others. The use of these “e-Health” solutions have increased the performance of the healthcare sector during the pandemic. Mainly because healthcare providing institutions were able to offer the same qualitative medical care from a distance (Iyanna et al., 2022).

A consequence of a digital transformation is the training of end-users who must adapt to the new situation by changing their behavior and accept a new method of working. In the healthcare sector, it is not only the employees in a hospital, such as doctors, nurses and front desk staff that need to be trained. Patients also need guidance to make a digital transformation a success. With a rapid change in new technologies, it is important to keep examining new methods to train end-users as efficiently as possible. Research by Martin et al. (2013) confirms this by stating the following: “*As there is no single method to deliver training, trainers continue to search for the best method to present targeted information to trainees*”.

This research continues to examine digital learning and its impact on the pace of (digital) change. The COVID-19 pandemic gave digital learning more potential since it enabled remote training (Pokhrel & Chhetri, 2021). Especially in education, since the COVID-19 pandemic there has been new research published on the impact of e-learning (Apostolidis et al., 2022; Maatuk et al., 2022; Adeoye et al., 2020).

Literature is still missing research on digital learning and its impact on the pace of (digital) change in hospitals. In the healthcare sector, e-learning in the form of demo videos cloud have a positive impact on the pace of change. According to Baker (2012) demo videos assist people “*in understanding key concepts, skills and understandings*”. Other researchers explain more benefits of digital learning which also apply for demo videos (Sharin, 2021; Maatuk et al., 2022; Adeoye et al., 2020). E-learning methods are flexible because, for example, employees can choose at what time they want to learn. The same goes for patients who, for example, have the ability to learn how to sign up for their appointment online from home via the internet. E-learning can help the board of a hospital to save costs such as having to invite instructors to a traditional on-site class (Maatuk et al., 2022).

This research aims to explore the impact that training with demo videos has on the pace of change in hospitals in the Netherlands and thereby bridge the existing knowledge gap. This study is relevant for hospitals that face challenges in training their employees and patients during a digital transformation and can help provide insights on how to improve the pace of change. Additionally, academic researchers can use this research as a basis for future follow-up research. For example, the results can be used to examine more possibilities with digital training in other sectors.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The COVID-19 pandemic forced organizations to put a stop on their daily operations or adapt their operations in order to offer the products and/or services remotely. Healthcare in particular was challenged in these times. In addition to providing healthcare, hospitals had to digitize processes to avoid physical contact with people as much as possible. This digital transformation also meant that doctors and patients, among others, had to quickly learn how to work with technological innovations.

Apostolidis et al. (2022) examined the impact of rapid end-user technology adoption in schools during the pandemic. The study found that rapid technology adoption had several functional consequences affecting end-users. The rapid adoption of unfamiliar technology creates challenges for end-users. As a result, time and effort, training and preparation, or familiarity with the technology are required to enable technology adoption. Training thus appears to impact rapid technology adoption.

Existing literature already describes the benefits of digital learning. There is no existing literature yet on the positive impact of digital learning on the pace of change within hospitals in the Netherlands. This study will try to fill this gap by identifying the impact of demo videos on the pace of change so that digital transformations can be deployed with more knowledge on how to implement new technologies in a timely manner. Demo videos are defined as training with (demonstration) videos that show the end-user the new technologies and how to use the new technologies. Iyanna et al. (2022) examined user resistance to digital change. The research by Iyanna et al. (2022) states that training of employees and patients, to enable them to work with the new technologies, takes time and thus influences the pace of change.

The goal is to explore what online provided demonstration videos can do in the healthcare sector to provide aid with these challenges, as demo videos are used to train end-users to use the newly implemented system or tool.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The research question: “*What is the influence of demo videos as a training method on the pace of digital transformation in the healthcare sector?*” is formulated for the goal of this research. The question reflects the current knowledge gap in the existing literature. The variables have been defined and analyzed by literature research. To help answer the research question, sub-questions have been formulated.

The first sub-question: “*To what extent do the characteristics flexibility and engagement influence the user acceptance of digital changes in the healthcare?*” will give insights on how characteristics of demo videos will influence user acceptance of changes in the healthcare.

The second sub-question: “*How does the user acceptance influence the pace of change?*” will provide insights on the relationship between user acceptance and pace of digital changes.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL & THEORY

Based on the available literature and formulated research questions different variables and relationships can be recognized. While the goal of this research is to prove the positive effect between demo videos and pace of change, there are multiple (sub-)hypotheses. The figure below illustrates these hypotheses and the variables.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

- **H1:** The use of demo videos results in more engagement of the user.
- **H2:** The use of demo videos results in a more flexible way to train end-users.
- **H3:** Higher engagement of the user increases the user acceptance
- **H4:** The flexibility of training with demo videos increases the user acceptance
- **H5:** Increase of user acceptance results in a higher pace of change of digital transformations

Demo videos, engagement & flexibility

The conceptual model begins with the variable “demo videos”. As explained in the problem statement, the research in this paper will examine if demo videos can improve the pace of change for digital transformations within (Dutch) hospitals. More interesting, how specific elements of demo videos can influence the pace of change.

A research by Beheshti et al. (2018) explains what benefits and disadvantages demo videos will provide. Firstly, the authors make a reference to another previous research which states the following: “*Study offers individuals to learn novel ideas more conveniently and quickly while information is delivered in visual and verbal form simultaneously*”. A main benefit of learning through visuals and online instructions is the engagement it creates when properly set up (Beheshti et al., 2018). Secondly, because of the flexibility of demo videos learners will more likely follow the instructions. Online available demo videos can be viewed whenever the end-user wants to and also when they need it in the future it will still be available. As the research of Beheshti et al. (2018) explains “*The most significant benefits of instructional videos are that learners can stop, rewind, pause and then manipulate the timeline of studying*”.

The paper of Beheshti et al. (2018) describes more

advantages (and disadvantages) of demo videos. For this research the elements “engagement” and “flexibility” are especially important. There is research (Surr & Gates, 2017) that confirms that elements such as engagement are key factors in training hospital personnel. The creation of engagement within the training is helping with delivering the knowledge. When the training material and information is relevant to the employee’s role, engagement will be higher (Surr & Gates, 2017). However, this research also discourages the use of online training because of the flexibility the trainees have. In contrast, it is not proven that flexible training does not lead to a higher user acceptance. Surr & Gates (2017) explain that the use of videos can enhance “*learner reactions and positive outcomes for learner confidence and self-efficacy*”. This research will use the findings of Surr & Gates (2017) to examine if flexibility can be beneficial in combination with high engagement and the use of digital instructional videos.

User acceptance

Davis (1989) explained with the TAM model how to measure the user acceptance of technological changes (a modern term is “digital transformation”). According to the TAM model there are two factors that have an effect on the user acceptance of technologies; Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. While there are papers about variables that influence the TAM model, it is not examined how different methods of training can enhance the user acceptance.

However, there is a research paper written by Aggelidis and Chatzoglou (2009) about the factors that will influence end-users in hospitals to use the “*state of the art technology*”. The research by Aggelidis and Chatzoglou (2009) has proved that training of personnel has a positive influence on the ease of use, and thus it can positively influence the user acceptance. Also, training has a positive influence on behavioral intention. This means that training end-users significantly enhances the degree in which end-users are willing to change their behavior (remove resistance).

The theory combined from the previous section forms the

basis for this research. Most importantly, how these concepts can positively influence the pace of change, based on the theory in the next section.

Pace of Change

The last variable in the model is pace of change. As explained in the previous section, this research will try to prove that using demo videos can increase the pace of change. Pace of change in this context means the speed at which a hospital can implement a new technology that will improve the quality, and efficiency, of healthcare.

A research from Mihai & Cretu (2017) states that digital transformations are mostly about change and leadership. Also, the research paper states that organizations need to (rapidly) develop the right skills by “making training as a consistent activity followed by skill gap analysis”. So, pace of change goes along with using the best fitting training method.

To conclude the theory, a research by Al-Gahtani & King (1999) explains key factors to implementing information systems. The authors state that the ability to identify, predict and manage the acceptance of end-users is important during the introduction and implementation of an information system. Although this does not prove the fifth hypothesis from figure 1, it confirms that end-users and the perceiving differences of end-users play a role in a digital transformation. This theory will be examined in the interviews.

METHOD

To answer the research question, literature research and survey research was conducted. These methods generated secondary, primary and qualitative data that is used in this study. The research has a deductive approach which means that hypotheses are formed based on general existing research and that data is collected and analyzed to test the hypothesis (Saunders & Lewis, 2017).

Literature Research

There is no existing literature on the specific effect that demo videos have on the pace of change of digital transformations in hospitals, especially not with the available technology of the last few years. By conducting literature research secondary data was collected and analyzed which helped conducting a theoretical analysis to support the results of the survey research.

The literature is used to partly explain or emphasize the relationships that are examined in this paper, see figure 1 for a visual overview. It describes the importance generating more knowledge on the following topics:

- benefits and disadvantages of demo videos;
- engagement created by demo videos;
- flexibility of training with demo videos;
- influence of training with demo video on the user acceptance;
- the use of demo videos to increase the pace of change.

Survey research

To collect primary qualitative data, semi-structured interviews were conducted. This form is chosen because it ensures the validity and accuracy of this research. Instead of questionnaires, semi-structured interviews provide rich information as respondents can use their own words to answer the questions. Thereby it also gives the researchers the opportunity to address specific dimensions while they also leave space for the study participants to introduce new meanings into the research and to further explain these meanings (Galletta, 2013).

The semi-structured interviews are developed by following the framework of (Kallio et al., 2016). First, it is determined whether semi-structured interviews are the appropriate format for this study. This is the case because it allows the researchers to focus on the issues that are meaningful for the participants and explore the participants' perceptions and opinions about the topics. Secondly, existing research is analyzed to gain extended knowledge about the substance of this research. This knowledge is thirdly used to formulate the interview questions which direct the conversation toward the topics of the research and ensure dialogue during the interview sessions. All interview questions are in Dutch as both the researchers and the study participants are from The Netherlands and speak Dutch. The questions can be found in appendix 1. Main themes of the interview are digital transformation, training methods, demo videos, change management and user acceptance. Follow-up questions are used to stimulate the conversation flow. These are partly preformulated and partly spontaneous when more in-depth information about a specific topic or experience is required. After determining what questions should be asked, according to the framework, the interview should be tested for the coverage and relevance that it should generate. Due to the limited time frame, it was decided to skip this step and proceed to the last step. Namely, conducting the semi-structured interview.

Sample

Because research about the usage of demo videos as a training method in hospitals is limited, semi-structured interviews were conducted. Experts in digital transformation in the healthcare sector have been interviewed to gain more knowledge about the benefits of different training methods that are used in healthcare and what influence demo videos may have on the pace of change of digital transformation. The sample chosen in this study had to consist of people who have approximately four or more years experience as a CIO of a Dutch hospital.

Because qualitative research is being conducted, it is difficult to determine how many participants were needed for this study. Because different study designs are used, it is difficult to determine and set general rules for when the point of data saturation is reached. Therefore, according to Fusch & Ness (2015), it is important to look at data as rich and thick. Data is rich if it is qualitative and thick as the quantity is high. Also, Fusch & Ness (2015) say that data saturation can already be achieved with a number of six interviews. Due to the limited time frame, two interviews have been conducted. As a result, the thickness of the data is not high, but the richness is high because reliable experts in the field are interviewed.

Due to the absence of a clear sampling frame, a non-probability sampling design is chosen. The participants were selected by judgment sampling based on their expertise and experience. The CIOs are experts and their experience and knowledge contribute greatly to the richness of this research. The following participants have been interviewed (table 1):

Table 1: Research participants

#	Background participant
1	- Former CIO Bravis Ziekenhuis, Roosendaal & Bergen op Zoom
2	- Former CIO Amphia ziekenhuis, Breda

Coding

To structure and analyze the collected data from the interviews, an open-coding analysis technique is used. The open-coding analysis technique makes the analyzing

and concluding of the interviews easier (Williams & Moser, 2019). The answers given by the interviewees have been repeatedly read and the data is categorized by all three researchers. In order to avoid errors in translation and interpretation, the interview questions and answers are not translated to English.

Reliability & validity

As already mentioned, the data retrieved from the interviews is reliable due to the set criteria for the respondents. Also, the validity of the interviews is increased by making questions based on existing theory. For instance, questions are derived from the TAM model (Davis, 1989) and from the research by Al-Gahtani & King (1999). Secondary data is used to confirm or contradict data from the interviews and also to prove the hypotheses of figure 1. Papers are used in the previous section to emphasize certain variables and relationships.

To improve the reliability of this research, the available research papers that were used during this research must comply with a set of requirements, namely that the paper has at least over fifteen citations, uses more than twenty references (depending on the size of the paper) and it needs to be published in a journal that is commonly known in the field of information management. The existing research will be retrieved from multiple highly recommended databases. Mainly from Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, EBSCO, JSTOR and ResearchGate.

RESULTS

As mentioned in the method section, the research is conducted by means of literature research and survey research. The literature research is used to confirm and reason the interview results. The interviews were conducted with former CIOs of a hospital in the Netherlands. Once the interview participants were interviewed, the interviews were transcribed¹ and coded. The codes are shown in Table 2.

¹The data from the interviews are published on Dataverse, with the following title "Interview data for research paper "Digital transformations in healthcare: Improving the pace of change by demo videos"." Due to review of the documents the transcripts are also separately uploaded on the conference publish tool.

Table 2: Coding interviews

Code group	Code	# of quotes	Sample Quotations
Budget		3	
	Costs affect user acceptance of board members / usefulness demo videos	3	<i>“If you can buy recorded videos from a company, I think that will save on costs, instead of a consultant having to come by 10 times and ask 10 times his hourly rate.”</i>
Complexity of change		4	
	Complexity of change influences usefulness of demo videos	4	<i>“The flavors you choose to train you have to consider in my experience to how complex something is (...) the more difficult the more personal attention”</i>
Engagement		9	
	Demo videos will not have a positive effect on engagement without classroom training	4	<i>“Because if you don’t offer it classroom setting, you will not reach many doctors”</i>
	Demo videos will not have a positive effect on engagement without personal attention	2	<i>“Furthermore, I think there is role determined for personal attention (...) then personal attention comes to light.”</i>
	Age affects engagement when using demo videos	1	<i>“Because you see that as soon as there is a mix of generations (...) generations do have an influence.”</i>
	Interest in technology affects engagement when using demo videos	2	<i>“Next to generations, interest plays a role.”</i>
Flexibility		2	
	Demo videos increase flexibility	2	<i>“Anytime, anywhere (...) I think those are major benefits.”</i>
Pace of change		2	
	User	2	<i>“But it really depends</i>

	acceptance has a positive relationship to pace of change		<i>on the adoption by patients (...) that causes delay”</i>
Pace of user acceptance		3	
	Flexibility improves user acceptance	3	<i>“I think the answer is yes (...) speeds up the learning curve of your users.”</i>
Size of change		3	
	Type of training method depends on size of change	3	<i>“What is important: how big is the group? (...) if the group is small, I would never go for digital or classroom training.”</i>
User acceptance		4	
	Demo videos improve user acceptance	4	<i>“So, the videos help (...) what helps studying for a lot of people”</i>

Engagement of end-users during digital change

In the healthcare sector, demo videos do have an effect on the engagement of end-users. However, according to experiences of the interviewees, the demo videos are not sufficient enough to get (all) the end-users properly engaged. A major percentage, 95% of the employees according to former CIO of Bravis hospital, of the end-users of a digital tool or system in a hospital are still depending on personal attention while getting trained.

Personal attention is still required because of several reasons. Namely, busy schedules, complexity, age and if the end-users have a general interest in technology.

Employees of hospitals, in particular doctors, have busy schedules. The engagement towards training for a new digital change is therefore low on their priority list. As a result, classroom training is used to manipulate the schedule of the end-users and claim the attention. Due to the nature of training by use of demo videos, the end-users will be likely not to train as they would be able to prioritize the training themselves.

The complexity of the digital transformation has a role in the engagement of end-users when using demo videos. When implementing a very complex system, the demo videos are automatically more complex and/or longer in time which in the experience of the former CIO of

Amphia hospital negatively impacts the engagement of the end-users. More complexity requires more personal attention when training.

In the experience of the CIOs, the age of the end-user influences the engagement. As technology has become more relevant in the last few decades, the familiarity of technology is generally less with older people. That generally results in less motivation to be engaged in the training process. Therefore, more personal attention is required.

The same reasoning goes for end-users with a lesser personal interest in technology. The motivation to learn new technologies using demo videos is lower when there is less interest in the specific digital change.

In contrast, demo videos will positively influence the engagement for the group that has a general interest in technology and is familiar with data and technology (possibly related to age), assuming that the digital change is not too complex. This is because the combination of visual and auditory training is a good way of training for people. This statement is proved by the research of Beheshti et al. (2018). An effect of demo videos is according to this paper described as follows *“The instructional videos are basically visual. The combination of educational audio and images allow end-users to obtain information easily particularly, the knowledge that is fundamentally visual.”*

Flexibility of demo videos

Demo videos offer flexibility to training. Being able to train yourself as an end-user, as the former CIO of Amphia hospital explained, at *“any time and any place”* removes the constraints of scheduled (classroom) training. It enables end-users to execute what they learn from the videos right after they have watched it.

This flexibility improves the user's acceptance. The former CIO of Bravis hospital explained: *“Because you reach people who want to learn on their own occasion and because you give people the opportunity to use the video as reference material when you do not remember how it worked. Again, on their own occasion. These two increase the learning curve, speed up the learning curve of your users actually”*. Flexibility is thus an important factor that helps to improve user acceptance.

Budget

An interesting insight resulting from the interviews is that cost reduction is a major benefit of the demo videos. For ‘simple’ changes, simple training by the use of videos can be a sufficient and cheaper option. Hospital

board members play a part in a digital change. Budget and cost have been mentioned multiple times during the interviews. Especially when it comes to removing resistance from board members of hospitals. Therefore, demo videos can play a role of removing resistance from members of the board.

The relationship between user acceptance and pace of change

According to the interviewed specialists, user acceptance has an impact on the pace of change. Firstly, the adoption of technology for patients, doctors, nurses and board members can cause delays. Secondly, *“It helps to improve the skills of the people, the patients, nurses and doctors (...) and it improves rapidly applying, implementing those digital changes”*. The former CIO of Bravis talked about the effect of using demo videos. The impact of user acceptance and demo videos is positive.

Usage of demo videos & learning satisfaction

A research paper by Nagy (2018) has proven that the TAM model, usage of online instructional videos and learning satisfaction have an impact on each other. This research is based on the education sector. Although, the relationships are also interesting for this research. There are three relevant relationships described in this paper that are proven with statistical analysis. Firstly, learning performance has a direct positive effect on learning satisfaction. This implies that when a user performs well in the training, the user will as a result be satisfied with their progression. Secondly, video usage had a significant positive effect on learning performance. So, it can be concluded that when videos are used to train end-users the trainees will show better results. Lastly, learner-teacher interaction has a strong positive effect on learning performance. Nagy (2018) has examined that when there is interaction between the trainer and trainee, the performance of the trainee will be better. These three relationships, again, confirm that engagement and the use of videos enhance the learning experience and how end-users interpret new subjects.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study came from both literature research and survey research. In analyzing the results, some interesting interpretations emerged.

Firstly, there is a relationship between training with demo videos and the user acceptance. It is clear that the flexibility that comes with demo videos is beneficial to the user's acceptance of technology. However, the engagement of the end-users when using demo videos as a training method can be either improved or not, depending on several conditions. As mentioned in the results, the engagement differs due to busy schedules of people, the complexity of a new digital system, age of those to be trained and if the end-users have a general interest in technology.

These dependencies can be interpreted as variables influencing the relationship between the demo videos and the user acceptance. Therefore, the dependencies: workload personnel, complexity, age and general interest in / familiarity with technology can be seen as moderating variables. The emergent model is visualized in figure 2.

Figure 2: Emergent model

Based on this research, flexibility and engagement do have a positive impact on the user acceptance in the healthcare sector. The combination of the two can also improve cost reduction, which helps reduce resistance from board members of hospitals.

The downside of demo videos is clearly the lack of personal attention. Personal attention is still imperative for the healthcare sector due to characteristics of the end-users. Currently, most of the training is given in classroom settings or one on one as the personal attention is crucial for adoption. Firstly, because digital change generally is not a priority for employees. Secondly,

because the change can be too complex in the eyes of the end-users. Lastly, the training is more effective when it is applicable for the situations the end-users find themselves in. That means that demo videos require customization in order for it to be more effective for end-users instead of general demo videos that are applicable for every end-user such as videos that explain the general functions of Microsoft Word.

In the end, both the existing literature and the interviews confirm that videos and engagement improve learning experience and therefore user acceptance. Furthermore, it improves the pace of change.

CONCLUSION

The goal of this research is to determine if demo videos positively influence the pace of change of digital transformations in Dutch hospitals. To determine this statement, the hypotheses from figure 1 will be answered.

H1 is partly true, because the data both confirms and contradicts it. The research by Beheshti et al. (2018) has examined the advantages of demo videos, including engagement and flexibility. In contrast, the respondents state that the triggering of engagement depends on the type of end-user.

H2 is, according to the respondent, also true, because digital videos make it possible to train yourself as a user “anywhere at any time”. Based on the literature research and answers from the respondents, the elements “engagement” and “flexibility” of a training do positively influence the user acceptance. Lastly, the last hypothesis is also true. Al-Gahtani & King (1999)

confirms that prediction of user behavior and reactions enhance the digital transformation process. Thereby, the respondents confirm that the acceptance and cooperation of end-users positively influence the pace of change. With these answers to the hypotheses, it is concluded that demo videos positively influence the pace of change.

This research contributes to society by giving insight into the benefits of training with demo videos in the healthcare sector. With the conclusions made in this paper the decision for hospitals to invest in digital training methods with demo videos should be easier. The results show relations between demo videos and the pace of change of digital transformations. The findings contribute to making hospitals more digitally resilient, by enhancing the speed at which hospitals can implement new technologies.

The paper contributes to academia by giving more insights in digital training methods and variables influencing the user acceptance and pace of change. Also, it delivers a contribution to research about the healthcare sector and digital transformations. Further research could expand this, which is explained in the next section.

Limitations & further research

There are a few limitations to this research, which also could inspire further research. The first limitation regards the sample size. In this research only two respondents were interviewed. The paper is developed within a limited time due to a strict deadline, hence the limitation of the sample size. Increasing the sample size of interviewees will increase the reliability of the research. Still, to maintain the reliability two respondents with different experiences were independently selected.

Secondly, to extend and statistically prove the relationships in figure 1, an experiment should be conducted. The interviews provide insights into the variables of this research. In the previous section conclusions about these variables and their relationships were made. These conclusions cannot be said to be certainly true. The conclusions are insights based on collected data and could be triggers for further research. To further expand these insights it can be tested, in an experiment, which training method provides the best results.

As mentioned in the interviews, a mixture of physical training and online instructional videos (blended learning) can be beneficial for the pace of change and still maintain the same learning performance. Future research should focus on the possibilities with blended

learning and the use of emerging technologies like Virtual Reality.

Finally, further research should examine how doctors can be stimulated regarding new technologies in their field. The interviewees mentioned that, especially the older generation of doctors, are not willing to free time and learn about the new technologies. This plays a role in the user acceptance, but also how doctors are stimulated to use this technology. If CIOs and change managers know how to get this group to move forward, it could be beneficial for the pace of change and quality of healthcare.

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APPENDIX**Appendix A - Interview questions (Dutch)**

Doelen voor het einde van het interview:

- Zijn demo videos efficient;
- Hoe binnen ziekenhuizen personeel getraind wordt;
- Effect, op de snelheid van implementatie, van bepaalde manieren van trainen;
- Change Management binnen ziekenhuizen;
- Valkuilen digitale transformaties binnen ziekenhuizen

***Introductie**

Voorstellen, doel van het interview en het onderzoek uitleggen, vragen naar functie en ervaring geïnterviewde en of het opgenomen mag worden.*

Digitale transformatie / snelheid

1. Welke digitale transformaties heeft u tijdens uw rol als CIO doorgemaakt?
2. Wat zijn uw ervaringen als CIO met de snelheid van digitale transformaties en ziekenhuizen?
 - a. Welke factoren waren van invloed op de snelheid en wat zijn best practices?
3. Wat is het belangrijkste om tijdens digitale transformaties te monitoren?

Trainingsmethoden + demo videos

4. Werd er bij het ziekenhuis waar u werkte gebruikt gemaakt van demo video's om personeel te trainen?

- a. Zo ja, hoe was dit dan ingericht en waarom werd gekozen voor deze methode?
- b. Zo nee, waarom wordt dit niet gebruikt? En welke manier(en) werd dan gebruikt?
- c. Wat maakt deze methode(n) goed en wat zijn nadelen hieraan?
- d. Wat zou het effect zijn als deze methode vervangen wordt door een (moderne) demo video(s)?

5. Waar liep u tegen aan tijdens het trainen van het personeel of om het personeel mee te krijgen met de digitale transformatie?
6. Waar liep het personeel tegen aan in de training? En waar liep u tegenaan?
7. Welke factoren van de huidige manier waarop mensen worden getraind hebben een positieve invloed op de snelheid van de digitale verandering?

Change management / user acceptance

8. Op wat voor manier kunnen medewerkers doorgeven dat er problemen zijn?
9. Is er genoeg budget beschikbaar voor het realiseren van een goede training? Of wordt dit geld niet beschikbaar gesteld?

Conclusie

10. Kijkend naar uw antwoorden, zou u met uw ervaringen kunnen concluderen dat pace of change beïnvloed kan worden door demo videos (d.m.v. user acceptance)?

***Afsluiten:** Samenvatten, vragen wat de geïnterviewde nog aan adviezen heeft, interesses in het onderzoek of de notulen/coderingen?*